

A

Project

On

“Service Sector in India”

Submitted towards the completion of the Course „Project-1“, Semester IV

Of

Bachelors of Business Administration

Of

Symbiosis Centre for Management Studies, Pune

Batch 2020-23

Under the Supervision of

Dr. Sameera Raees

Submitted by

Name of the student – Utkarsh Navandar

PRN NO – 20020621478

Name of the student – Shubhangi Jain

PRN NO - 20020621435

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The comprehensive project report assigned to us by SCMS Pune, Symbiosis International (Deemed University) was a great opportunity that helped us in getting insights into the present & future of the service business in India which will surely be helpful to us in nearby future. The entire journey of bringing together the various components of our topic was full of ups and downs but it helped us to grow in a way or so. We worked as a team together which helped a lot in putting up ideas and opinions which were diverse to make our entire project more dynamic.

My professor in-charge Dr. Sameera Raees also helped us from the beginning of our project by introducing us to the concept of research projects and clarifying all the steps we should take up to get the desired outcome. We would also like to appreciate the efforts taken up by our batch coordinator Varsha ma'am for cooperating with us and guiding us towards the essentials while dealing with some of the difficulties faced during the Covid-19 situation.

Annexure A

Project-1

Project Proposal Form

This is to inform that title of the Project-1 that I will be undertaking

Under the guidance of Dr. Sameera Raees

is “Service Sector in India”

Name of the student: Utkarsh Navandar & Shubhangi Jain

Batch 2020-2023

PRN NO: 20020621478 & 2002061435

Signature of the Student - Utkarsh Navandar

Shubhangi Jain

Name of the Faculty Supervisor Dr. Sameera Raees

Designation: Faculty

Signature of the faculty – Dr. Sameera Raees

DECLARATION BY THE STUDENT

I the undersigned solemnly declare that the report of the project work entitled Doing Service Business In India, is based on our own work carried out under the supervision of Dr. Sameera Raees. I assert that the statements made and conclusions drawn are an outcome of the project work. I further declare that to the best of my knowledge and belief that the project is not a copy or an adaptation/ improvisation of the existing project. Due mention has been made of various work which has been referred to in this study and required permissions has been taken for the same. This Project report is being submitted towards fulfillment of the course Project 1

(Signature of the Student)

Name of the Student – Utkarsh Navandar

Roll No.: 1289

PRN No. 20020621478

Batch 2023

(Signature of the Student)

Name of the Student – Shubhangi Jain

Roll No.:1284

PRN No. 20020621435

Batch – 2023

CERTIFICATE BY FACULTY SUPERVISOR

This to certify that the report of the project submitted is the outcome of the experiential project work entitled Doing Service Business In India carried out by Utkarsh Navandar and Shubhangi Jain Roll No 1289 and 1284 respectively of Batch under my guidance and supervision for the fulfillment of the Course- Project 1.

To the best of my knowledge, the report:

- i) Embodies the work of the candidate him/herself,
- ii) Has duly been completed,
- iii) Is up to the desired standard for the purpose of which it is submitted.

(Signature of the Faculty)

Name: Dr. Sameera Raees

Designation:

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The goal of our study paper was to focus on the "Service Sector in India" and examine what the future holds for the service sector in India. This research aims to uncover the significant changes in the service sector through time and their overall impact on business structure. This research paper also discusses the importance of services in the modern economy, the reasons for their emergence in India, and the shift in this sector, as services play a major and crucial role in the Indian economy's pace of growth. It has become one of the fastest-growing sectors on the global landscape as a result of its emergent nature, contributing significantly to global output and employment growth. Under this study paper, we have explored elements affecting the Service Business in India, what services contribute the most to GDP, consumer patterns, infrastructure, and many other topics that directly or indirectly function as a catalyst. We used primarily two types of data collection methods to complete this research project: primary and secondary data collection. After doing various surveys we landed up with the conclusion that rise in service sector just started & it will see a huge surge in terms of investments, government initiatives, market shares, etc in years to come..

Contents

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	2
Signature of the Student - Utkarsh Navandar	3
DECLARATION BY THE STUDENT	4
CERTIFICATE BY FACULTY SUPERVISOR	5
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	6
INTRODUCTION	9
DEMOGRAPHICS.....	10
RELIGIONS IN INDIA	11
SOCIO ECONOMIC STATUS.....	12
Agriculture.....	12
Climate Change	12
Education.....	12
Healthcare, Water and Sanitation	12
Poverty Alleviation.....	13
ECONOMY	14
Gdp (gross domestic product).....	14
Employment	15
Balance Of Payments.....	15
SERVICE SECTOR IN INDIA.....	17
Market size of Service Industry.....	18
Services majorly contributing to GDP.....	18
IT-BPM/ Fintech Sector	18
Tourism.....	19
Logistics & Transportation.....	20
E-Commerce Sector.....	20
CONSUMPTION PATTERN	21
Demographic profile:.....	21
Income profile:	23
Future of Consumption post the pandemic.....	25
INFRASTRUCTURE IN INDIA	25
RATIONALE OF STUDY	27

OBJECTIVES OF STUDY	28
DATA COLLECTION METHOD	29
Primary method	29
Secondary source data	30
Literature Review	30
DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION.....	33
FINDINGS	36
BIBLIOGRAPHY	37
APPENDICES	39

INTRODUCTION

Our research paper focuses on India's service sector business & its potential to grow in the future. Actions that help businesses but do not result in a tangible product are referred to as services. For example, information technology is a business service that supports a range of other business services including shipping, procurement, and finance. The majority of today's enterprises are leaning toward such specialist business offerings. Zomato, once again, is a business service that delivers food to your door. If you want to transfer money to your friend or relative who stays far away from you, now you don't have to walk along the lane to reach out to the bank & stand in a queue, it's all a matter of a click & all you need to do is follow the tagline of the very famous brand "Paytm Karo!" with Paytm. Well from paying E-bills to buying groceries everything can be done using a phone & is just a matter of a click. There are a plethora of more examples in these fields. Decades after Decades a new name is added to this list & so when it comes to offering services, India is becoming increasingly competitive and giving other countries a run for their money. A big number of international countries chose India as their business hosting partner, and some even opt to create a branch office there. Service sectors leads to incredible growth & stand as the major contributor towards GDP. It is the second largest employer after agriculture. Talking about the market shares of Service businesses in India, it contributed 55.39 percent to India's Gross Value Added at the current price in FY20

Well, all of these points made a greater impact & pushed the GOI to recognize the necessity of encouraging growth in the services sector, and as a result, it provided a variety of incentives in fields like health care, tourism, education and others. This is just a mere introduction of the service sector business; every details have been covered while doing this research paper.

DEMOGRAPHICS

India being the second country in terms of population in South Asia & 7th largest country by land area & the most populous democracy in the world. India is one of the oldest civilizations in the world and a mosaic of multicultural experiences. The country has a rich heritage and numerous attractions, making it one of the most popular tourist destinations in the world. It is expanded in an area of 32,87,263 square kilometers, extending from the snow-capped highlands of the Himalayas to in the south. As the seventh largest country in the world, India, unlike other parts of Asia, is surrounded by sea on all sides. This gives the country a special geographical position.

Figure 1 Location of India

Figure 2 Population Graph of India 1960-2020

RELIGIONS IN INDIA

India is the world's 2nd most populated country. Hinduism contributing about 78.18% of total population. The religion has always played a major role in Indonesia's history. Government has identified 6 major religions which are as followed:

1. Buddhism
2. Christianity
3. Hinduism
4. Islam
5. Jainism
6. Sikhism

Figure 3 Religions In India

SOCIO ECONOMIC STATUS

Agriculture

India ranks 2nd worldwide in agricultural outputs. As per 2018, this sector employed more than 50% of Indian workforce and contributed up to 18 percent of gross national product.

India is among the global producers of various crops such as wheat, rice, pulses, cotton and variety of vegetables.

Climate Change

India has started to suffer from climate changes in recent years. Heavy rainfall and heatwaves have become more common and severe, many places get flooded each year due to excessive rainfall and poor drainage systems while some places suffer from extreme heat. Some theories says that more than 50 coastal areas will be drowned by the year 2050 in India and low lying river beds will be sub merged under water. And, these not only affect the people lying in coastal areas but mostly affect the people who have a low income.

Education

India has made a great development in improving the quality of education, increasing primary and secondary schools and reducing the count of illiterate children.

These are the results of educational acts taken by the recent government to make a child educate compulsorily till the 5th Grade. Government offers mid day meal to poor children which not only motivates them to study but also assure their parents about securing the meal for their children.

Healthcare, Water and Sanitation

Healthcare is now considered one of the leading sector in terms of revenue & employment . As it's peers in ASia & Europe India's competitive advantage lies inprofessional healthcare. The average cost of surgest in India is 90% less than that of United states.

More than 90% people have access to basic water and 95% people have access to basic sanitation. According to 2003 report, 27% of waste water was being treated and

recycled and flown back into the streams, rivers and canals. The lack of adequate sanitation and healthy water has resulted into diseases such as diarrhoea and typhoid.

Poverty Alleviation

India has never counted its poor since 2011 but according to United nations its 364 million people suffering from poverty. Also, youth unemployment touched 23% in year 2019

Figure 4 Poor people in India (In percentage)

ECONOMY

India has emerged as one of the fastest growing economies across the world and counted as top three economic countries across the globe by year 2030.

Gdp (gross domestic product)

Year	GDP (in USD)	GDP Growth Rate	Annual Change in Growth Rate
2018	2.71 lakh crores USD	6.12%	(0.92%)
2019	2.87 lakh crores USD	4.18%	(1.94%)
2020	2.70 lakh crores USD	(7.9s7%)	(12.15%)

Figure 5 GDP of India in last three years

The GDP has fallen in past year mainly due to relatively lower growth in hospitality industry, mining and quarrying, construction and airline sector. India's real GDP has contracted by 7.97 in current financial year from a growth rate of 4.2 per cent in 2019-20, the contraction in the economy is mainly on account of the impact of the corona virus pandemic.

Employment

Year	Employment (According to EPFO{Employee Provident Fund Organisation})
2018	397 million
2019	400 million
2020	380 million

India saw an unemployment rate of over six percent at the start of 2020. Total lockdown caused a huge impact on life of people. Unemployment hit up to nearly 24 percent in April 2020. This was possibly a result shutting down of sectors and companies applying various cost cutting techniques to avoid losses. Sole traders and small employees were affected the most by covid 19 leading to 91 million people unemployed across the nation. More than 110 million people in Indian lost their jobs, including entrepreneurs and salaried workers. Agriculture, on the other hand, witnessed a 5% increase from farmers compared to fiscal year 2020.

Figure 6 fall of employment in India due to covid crisis

Balance Of Payments

The Balance of Payments (BoP) documents all monetary transactions between a country's citizens and the rest of the globe. The BoP account is made up of two parts: the current account and the capital account.

Figure 7 Primary Account Flows

Year	Current Account Balance- as % of GDP	Capital Account Balance-as % of GDP
2017	-1.84	3.45
2018	-2.11	2.02
2019	-0.85	2.89

Figure 8 Balance of Payments in recent years for India

SERVICE SECTOR IN INDIA

The service sector in India is a one-of-a-kind example of outlining conventional economic growth trends. Within just 50 years of independence, India's service economy has generated more than 60% of the country's GDP. However, it continues to employ only 25% of the workers. As a result, agriculture and industry continue to employ the vast majority of people. This offers a progressive task to India's destiny financial increase and necessitates out-of-the-field thoughts to help speedy harness the capability of India's provider industry. Invest India examines the offerings sector's contribution to the Indian economy, its triumphs, and capability facilitators for destiny truthful financial increase.

Figure 9 Service Sector distribution

Market size of Service Industry

	India	United States	China
Agriculture and Allied	15.4%	8%	7%
Manufacturing and Industry	23%	12%	40%
Services (Majority contribution by IT)	61.5%	80%	52%

Figure 10 GDP of Service Sector

Services majorly contributing to GDP

IT-BPM/ Fintech Sector

During monetary 12 months 2018-19, worldwide generation funding became 3.sixty five trillion Us Dollars. India has 1.23 billion cell telephones and 7,705 million net users. India has one of the maximum and most inexpensive information utilization prices withinside the world. 22 India's IT-BPM enterprise money owed for 8% of the country's GDP. With 3.nine

million employees, the enterprise is the biggest agency within the non-public sector. The Indian IT and BPM enterprise is predicted to attain USD 310 billion via way of means of 2020.

India has the world's second-maximum range of telephone connections. Telecom anticipates the installation of around 0.4 million kilometres of optical fibre cable to cover 163 thousand Gram Panchayats (GPS); nearly 1.51 lakh GPS are now service-ready.

Tourism

Travel and tourism was India's largest service industry, totaling \$234 billion at the end of 2018. With earnings of \$29.962 billion from January 2019 to December 2019, representing a 4.8 percent increase over the previous year, this industry has become one of India's major Foreign Exchange Earners.

Figure 11 Indian Tourism

Logistics & Transportation

Freight transportation, warehousing, fabric handling, defensive packaging, stock control, order processing, marketing, forecasting, and customer support are all a part of the logistics enterprise, that is an quintessential thing of the business-monetary gadget.

From the 1960s, while it changed into absolutely labor-intensive, to the prevailing day, with the mixing of a technology-orientated gadget that allows supply a extensive variety of logistical services, the Indian logistics enterprise has visible a sea change. Historically, the logistics enterprise changed into best worried with transportation and warehousing.

Currently, road transport is the primary form of transport in India, accounting for around 68 percent of freight transit. On Indian roadways, approximately 1.5 million trucks operate, with the number steadily increasing. Railways are less expensive than other modes of transportation and are favoured for delivering bulk items across large distances. The current condition of logistics in India is still in its early stages, and it has a long way to go before it can compete with its worldwide equivalents. The economy is highly fragmented, hampered by problems such as inadequate infrastructure and transportation conditions, complex tax rules, a lack of IT infrastructure, and a lack of industrial readiness.

E-Commerce Sector

E-commerce has absolutely modified the manner humans plan to do commercial enterprise in India. The Indian e-commerce sector is anticipated to attain two hundred billion dollars by 2026, up from \$38.5 billion in 2017. A surge in net and mobile usage has fueled maximum of the industry's growth. The number of net connections in India is expected to reach 776.45 million by September 2020, thanks to the 'Digital India' campaign. Sixty-one percent of total internet connections were in major cities and town areas, with ninety seven percent of wifi connections.

The Indian E-grocery industry is expected to grow at a CAGR of 57% to reach US\$ 18.2 billion in year 2024, from US\$1.9 billion in 2019. The amount of e-commerce orders in India climbed by 36% in the fourth quarter of 2020, with the personal care, beauty, and wellness (PCB&W) market benefiting the most.

Some of the biggest companies in service sectors are,

- Reliance Industries
- Axis Bank
- HDFC Bank
- NTPC
- Larsen And Turbo

CONSUMPTION PATTERN

As the concept of consumerism has progressively crept into India, marketing and distribution tactics have undergone significant modifications. The Indian market has become increasingly appealing to both international and domestic marketers. With a GDP of around \$2.5 trillion, India is the world's sixth-largest economy (third largest in PPP terms). Private consumption accounts for more than half of India's GDP. However, India's consumption habits are changing, and it will be interesting to watch what the future holds after the pandemic.

Demographic profile:

India's population situation is favourable. By 2030, millennials and Generation Z (those between the ages of 10 and 49) will account for 77% of the overall population. There will be 90 million new millennial-led families. Between the ages of 10 and 25, about 370 million people will be added to the young population.

The following shows India's Population Profile (Urban-Rural):

Source: World Bank

Figure 12 Population

We can see that 65.97 percent of the population lives in rural areas from the table above. Despite the fact that the rural population has been shrinking over time, it remains a significant factor in determining consumption. The urban population is predicted to grow in coming years as a result of growing urbanisation, technological improvements, and industry.

Working-age people make up 66% of the population. When a larger number of people join the working-age group, this number is likely to climb.

Private consumption is a direct factor of economic growth in a developing economy like India. Consumption is influenced by a number of factors, the most important of which is money. We can divide consumption into consumer discretionary and non-discretionary products for ease of understanding:

Discretionary are those goods & services which are noted under unessential goods like Jewellery, branded apparel, travel, restaurant etc. These are the industries that are most affected

by the ups and downs of the economy. If we take covid-19 into consideration this discretionary foods have been hit hard & will take time to recover.

Non-Discretionary are those products that are considered necessary for daily consumption like food beverages, household products, medicines, etc. These

goods are found not to be adversely affected by pandemic & recession. Covid 19 resulted in a panic scenario in consumers & their spending towards non-discretionary products increased.

Over the years, discretionary spending has been on the rise as can be seen from the following data:

Figure 13 Spending Pattern of Consumers

The accompanying graph shows that there has been a shift in consumption habits, with urban Indians contributing more than rural Indians.

Income profile:

Let us take a look into India's per capita income and consumption (at constant prices):

Figure 14 Pvt Expenditure

We can observe from the table above that income and consumption per capita have been rising over time. Consumption has expanded at a CAGR of 4.6 percent, while gross national income has grown at a CAGR of 4.6 percent and 4.9 percent, respectively. Though this provides a comprehensive picture of India's expanding consumption, we must also consider rural income levels and consumption patterns to fully comprehend rural consumption patterns.

Given below is the state-wise graph of income and expenditure of rural and semi-urban households:

Figure 15 State wise Income

As can be seen in the graph above, there is a significant income disparity among rural households in all states. This is due to the nature of the business and the amount of farmland holdings.

Future of Consumption post the pandemic

The Covid-19 pandemic has largely halted discretionary spending, resulting in a detrimental impact on economic growth. While a recovery is unlikely before 2020, how the economy strives for consumption in the future will be critical. While we have favourable demographics, there looks to be a question of future economic growth, employment, and income levels on the one hand. While the AatmaNirbhar Bharat package was designed to help India recover from the economic effects of the pandemic, it really accomplishes very little to boost aggregate demand. As a result, we believe that discretionary spending will stay low in the short to medium term.

INFRASTRUCTURE IN INDIA

India's population is expected to reach 1.5 billion by 2050. The government of and the population of India are striving for rapid growth, providing tremendous opportunities to meet the needs of people for various goods and services.

State governments are aware of the fact that the opportunities created by the opening up of the Indian economy cannot be realized without quality infrastructure services such as transportation, communications, energy and water transport. On the one hand, there are opportunities to meet the demand for goods and services, which requires high-quality infrastructure support. On the other hand, it is necessary to actively develop the road network, generate and distribute electricity, use oil and gas resources, and develop and connect ports, airports and railways for the transport of goods. Enterprises in the next two to three decades. The recent recognition by the Government of India of the need to upgrade these facilities to world class standard is supported by the emphasis on infrastructure development. Highway network with choice of network. Natural gas exploration expanded and the private sector was also invited in to participate in this effort. Access to communication has been improved many times and costs have been reduced. These are all good signs for business in India, but a lot of work needs to be done at the policy and provision level to ensure that private local and foreign companies can access infrastructure services to contribute to India's economic development.

Figure 16 Infrastructure Building

RATIONALE OF STUDY

The world is shifting to digital, so is India. From purchasing things from e-commerce to paying bills online, it all has scaled up gradually. Flipkart being the first successful shopping site in India laid the foundation stone & created opportunities for many business minds to grab the opportunity & enter the online market. Our honorable Prime Minister's campaign "Digital India" fueled it & scaled up the online market. Soon after this companies like Oyo, Zomato, Paytm, etc started acquiring a customer base in India. The growth of India's services industry is a rare illustration of traditional economic growth trends. In India's brief history of 75 years since independence, the service industry has grown to account for more than 60% of the country's GDP. However, it still only employs around a quarter of the workforce.

India's service sector accounts for bulk of GDP & market share in addition to attracting Foreign Investment. It also contributes significantly to export & employs a major section of people of india. The service Industry in India covers business, Banking & finance, Hospitality & many more areas. In FY21 this sector contributed to 55.39 of total GVA & an increase in it's GVA has been observed.

Also financial, real estate, and professional services grew at a Compound Annual Growth Rate of 11.68 percent (in Rs. terms) between FY16 and FY20, whereas trade, hotels, transportation, and communication grew at 11.68 percent (in Rs. terms) Compound Annual Growth Rate. This struck our mind & we finally landed up selecting the topic " Service Sector in India" & started doing research on it.

OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

The service industry includes a wide range of services like transport, e-commerce, telecommunication, banking, real estate, financial services etc. The major aim of the service industry is to facilitate the other economic sectors and to boost the GDP of the nation.

The objective of service industry includes:

- Employment boost
- Inputs and public services for the increase in economy
- Enhancing economic performance

DATA COLLECTION METHOD

While doing this research we have used various data collection method & got various insights from different people of different sections of the society. The major methods are listed below:

Primary method

Some ways through which we conducted primary research were reaching out to multiple vendors & getting their views on shifting to online mode of business in two entirely different city, we conducted surveys by rolling out google forms to our batch mates, seniors, friends & relatives & asking them few question regarding services in india & their scopes. Apart from this we tried reaching out to 2 industry experts who have been into service business in india since past few years. These three were the major source of our primary data collection Method & here is the list of questions that we asked our target audience.....

After going on with this method for 1 month we landed up getting a positive response towards our topic “doing service business in India”

As you can see above 145 people participated in the survey rolled out by us & majority of them says.....

Figure 17 Responses for our research paper

This is the graphical representation our survey. Since we were doing this Research paper project caged inside our 4 room walled with only little physical interaction people, we could only collect a few primary source data.

Secondary source data

As told earlier due to this pandemic we didn't get an opportunity for more physical surveys & all but thanks to 21st century & the online sources we had enormous of them. We used various government sites statistics, editorials of newspapers, elibraries & articles released by various organisations & other websites.

Literature Review

STUDIES	SAMPLE	PERIOD	SERVICE SECTOR
L. Das	Impact of Changes in Service Sector in India in Shaping the Future of Business & Society.	2014	The service sector was not considered important until recently. It requires less natural capital and more human capital.
Yanrui Wu	Service Sector Growth in China and India: A Comparison	2007	We have witnessed incredible growth in the economies of china and India. The growth was the result of dramatic developments of service sector.
Arpita Mukherjee	The Service Sector in India	2013	Although the service secotr in India is considered the largest & fastest growing sector of india with highest labour profuctivity but employment has been

			<p>in pace with the sector's contribution to GDP & has failed to provide the number or quality of jobs. There hasn't been any policy that leads to inclusive growth, and the sector's progress has been hampered. Also foreign Investment has been hampered. India being one of the top WTO members in terms of services exports & imports but export of services is too slow</p>
Sancharan Roy	Competitiveness in Service Sector: a case of hotel industry in India	2011	<p>Since many years manufacturing & allied industry have been facing competitiveness. Recently many researchers have started investigating the competitiveness of tourism & hospitality. The goal of this research paper was to identify the</p>

			most important competitive forces in this field.
F. Pathak	Employment Intensity of Service Sector in India	2010	The key to the economic performance India & other developed countries is a well-functioning service sector. This study is on employment intensity of service sector & examines the role of some macroeconomic factor in determining the same. It was concluded that growth in the service sector has increased over time but employment has slowed dramatically, resulting in a drop in employment elasticity.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The service sector is one of the fastest growing sectors in India. It employs more than 60% of the Indian workforce and contributes to more than 50% of the GDP. The service sector has a direct bearing on employment as well as growth in India. The government is trying to reduce regulations to encourage more investment in this sector while simultaneously introducing new products and services that will increase the demand for skilled labour.

The service sector is one of the largest contributors to GDP, owing its success primarily due to a large labour supply and strong productivity gains from information technology and other digital transformation initiatives.

Service-sector growth was driven by higher demand from consumer services, especially travel & tourism, construction, wholesale & retail trade, financial services, business process outsourcing (BPO), call centre etc.; which were supported by

The service sector in India is the third largest and fastest growing sector of the Indian economy. With a low investment rate and high service exports, India is gradually becoming a hub for information technology (IT) services, business process outsourcing (BPO) services, healthcare services and financial services.

The service sector in India grew by 6.2% in 2016-17 from 6% in 2015-16 on account of increased spending by tourists on hotels, travel and restaurants.

The service sector accounted for 53% of GDP in 2016-17 as against 51% in 2015-16.

The service sector accounted for 55.39% of total GVA in the 21 financial year. India's service sector GVA increased at a CAGR of 11.43% to Rs. 101.47 trillion (\$ 1,439.48 billion) in FY 20 from Rs. 68.81 trillion (1,005.30 billion US dollars) in fiscal year 2016. Between fiscal year 2016 and fiscal year 2020, financial, real estate and professional services grew at an average annual rate of 11.68% (in rupees), while commerce, hotels, transportation, communications and broadcast-related services recorded a CAGR of 10.98% (in rupees). The sector provides employment to a large part of the Indian population.

Exports of services make up a significant part of India's total exports. According to RBI, service exports were \$ 21.17 billion in April 2021, while imports were \$ 10.61 billion in 2021. The services category was ranked first in the inflow of FDI according to data published by the Ministry for the Promotion of Industry and Domestic Trade (DPIIT).

India / Nikkei / IHS Market Services Purchasing Managers' Index of Services Business Activity Index fell from 54.0 in April 2021 to 46.4 in May 2021 as production and orders fell due to restrictions imposed by COVID19 to contain the spread of the coronavirus .

With increased demand for remote consultation, the telemedicine market is driving growth in the healthcare sector. The Indian telemedicine market is anticipated to reach \$ 5.5 billion by 2025. Since its start, the Department of Health's eSanjeevani telemedicine programme has enabled 6 million (60 lakh) teleconsultations, allowing patient-to-doctor and doctor-to-doctor consultations. Home health care in India is expected to be worth \$10 billion by 2025. The Indian government intends to implement a credit incentive programme of Rs. 50,000 crore (\$ 6.8 billion) to improve the country's health infrastructure. The scheme will give businesses access to financing to expand hospital capacity or medical care, with the government acting as a guarantor.

Information Technology Business Process Management (ITBPM): Revenue in the ITBPM market is expected to be over \$ 191 billion in fiscal 2020, with a 7.7 percent growth rate. In FY21, the national income of the information technology industry is expected to be \$ 45 billion, with export revenue estimated to be \$ 150 billion. 10 cloud platforms that are expected to drive business transformation in sectors such as retail, telecommunications, and insurance are expected to do so. Drive growth in the IT and BPM sectors.

The government has implemented a number of policies to boost growth in the service industry. The government established the Export of Services of India Program (SEIS) to encourage the export of services from India by awarding customs credits for qualifying shipments. A premium of 35% of the net foreign currency from mode 1 and mode 2 services is granted. Furthermore, the 2015 mid-term trade policy review boosted the SEIS incentives

for notified services by 2%. Furthermore, the government has chosen 12 Champion Services Sectors Initiative sectors with the goal of developing cross-cutting action plans to fuel their growth.

FINDINGS

India's service sector had incredible growth after liberalization and major corporate changes in 1991, and it played a critical part in making India one of the world's fastest-growing economies in the last two decades. With the help of diverse commercial trade and investment models, the service sector has aided countries' integration with the global economy. India's service business has contributed the most to the country's GDP, foreign investment, and job creation over the last three decades with India ranked 6th in overall GDP and 8th in services GDP. Gradually as more & more market share will be captured by service businesses in India, there will be a rise in employment, income level, literacy, standard of living, etc.

The digital economy in India is predicted to be worth \$1 trillion by 2025. By the end of 2023, India's IT and business services sector is predicted to rise by 8% to US\$ 14.3 billion..

The introduction of the Goods and Services Tax (GST) resulted in the creation of a single national market and a reduction in the overall tax burden on goods. It is expected that the availability of GST input credit will reduce costs in the long run, resulting in a reduction in service prices.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Services Sector in India: Overview, Market Size, Growth, Companies. . IBEF. (n.d.). IBEF. Retrieved August 22, 2021, from <https://www.ibef.org/industry/services.aspx>

FIEO : Service Sector :- Scope, Steps, Categories, Incentives. (n.d.). Fieo. Retrieved August 22, 2021, from https://www.fieo.org/view_section.php?lang=0&id=0,23,24

Chegg.com. (2020, November 22). Chegg. <https://www.chegg.com/homework-help/questions-and-answers/benefit-tertiary-sector-particular-delivery-services-2020-effective-future-q62188420>

K, V. (2019, December 24). Service Marketing: Meaning, Scope, Objectives, Characteristics, Benefits. PreserveArticles.Com: Preserving Your Articles for Eternity. <https://www.preservearticles.com/service-marketing/service-marketing/31252>

The Service Industries Journal: Aims, Objectives and Scope. (n.d.). Taylor & Francis. Retrieved August 22, 2021, from <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/02642068300000002?needAccess=true&journalCode=fsij20>

A. (2020, December 21). Logistics Industry In India. Vakilsearch. <https://vakilsearch.com/advice/logistics-industry-in-india/>

Service Sector in India: A Paradigm Shift. (n.d.). Invest India. Retrieved August 22, 2021, from <https://www.investindia.gov.in/team-india-blogs/service-sector-india-paradigm-shift>

E-commerce in India: Industry Overview, Market Size & Growth| IBEF. (n.d.). IBEF. Retrieved August 22, 2021, from <https://www.ibef.org/industry/ecommerce.aspx>

Tourism Industry in India - FDI, Investment, Market Share. (n.d.). Invest India. Retrieved August 22, 2021, from <https://www.investindia.gov.in/sector/tourism-hospitality>

India Healthcare Tourism Portal of India, Medical Tourism in India. (n.d.). Indian Healthcare. Retrieved August 22, 2021, from <http://www.indiahealthcare.org/>

IT and BPM | Make In India. (n.d.). Make In India. Retrieved August 18, 2021, from <https://www.makeinindia.com/sector/it-and-bpm#:~:text=The%20IT%2DBPM%20industry%20in,USD%20310%20Bn%20by%202020>.

Services Sector in India: Overview, Market Size, Growth, Companies. . IBEF. (n.d.-b). IBEF. Retrieved August 16, 2021, from <https://www.ibef.org/industry/services.aspx#:~:text=India's%20services%20sector%20covers%20a,and%20services%20associated%20with%20construction>.

APPENDICES

In this graph, 30% of our responses said they use service sector/business daily. Other 27 say they use it almost every alternate day, 16.7% say they use it once a week and the remaining ones twice a week,

49.7% people believe that service sector is the reason behind growing GDP, 20% neglect the fact and other say maybe or may not be.

60% if them say E-Commerce is the reason they can relax and sit back. They believe E-Commerce has a scope to improve more and be more efficient.

35.9% of the people use E-commerce on weekly basis, 20% use fintech platform, 11.7% use logistics to courier their envelopes and packages to the destination, other 15% use tourism or tourism related websites to plan their travel and remaining 17% use other services.